
Work from Home and Its Influence on Women's Emotional Well-Being and Family Relationships

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ABSTRACT

Working from home (WFH) has had a deep impact on women's professional and personal lives. It has affected their family, emotional state, work-life balance, stress and concentration. The objective of this study is to analyse the impact of WFH on family dynamics and emotional well-being among women. It also aims to examine how WFH affects cognitive efficiency, stress levels and work-life balance, providing insights into both the benefits and challenges faced by women in a remote work environment. This study is based on 100 women from Delhi NCR, with data collected through interview method with the help of structured questionnaire. The research found that WFH allows women to spend more time with their families and increases family happiness. However, challenges such as blurred boundaries between work and personal life, increased stress and reduced concentration have also emerged. An interesting finding is that work hours and stress do not have a direct connection, suggesting that workload and household responsibilities may be the main causes of stress. This study can be useful for employers and policymakers in creating better policies and ensuring women's mental well-being. However, as this research is based on a limited area and a small group,

broader and long-term studies are needed. In the future, further research can be done on the challenges faced by women in different sectors, technological support and better remote work systems.

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1. Introduction

In recent years, the concept of WFH has become very important. Especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, when it was necessary to ensure people's safety while continuing economic activities, WFH was widely adopted (Al-Mansour & Al-Ajmi, 2020). This system gives women the opportunity to balance their work and family, allowing them to spend more time with their loved ones. However, there are also some negative aspects. Working from home blurs the line between work and personal life, which can sometimes increase mental pressure. Additionally, due to constant household and professional responsibilities, it becomes difficult to concentrate, which can also affect cognitive efficiency (Chen, 2021).

1.1. Overview of WFH(WFH) and Its Growing Relevance

In the beginning, WFH was seen as a new work system that completely changed the way people work. This change was especially noticeable in sectors that rely heavily on digital communication and online collaboration (Baruch & Yuen, 2000; Suratkon & Azlan, 2021). Due to technological advancements, people can communicate online without any interruptions, allowing them to maintain their productivity while working from home (Lopez-Leon et al., 2020). However, despite its many advantages, WFH has also created some new challenges. This is particularly true in fields like medical education, where concerns about teaching quality and management issues remain significant (Lopez-Leon et al., 2020). The shift to this system happened very rapidly due to the COVID-19 pandemic, bringing both new opportunities and many difficulties. To adapt to this new way of working, both employers and employees had to change their working styles and strategies (Baruch & Yuen, 2000; Suratkon & Azlan, 2021).

1.2. Challenges and Benefits of WFH for Women

The growing trend of WFH is having a deep impact on women's professional and personal lives. Research shows that WFH increases job satisfaction among women, helps them maintain a better balance between work and family and provides them with more flexibility (Kaufman & Taniguchi, 2021). Most

women consider it a good option because it allows them to manage both their household and work responsibilities more easily (Church, 2015). However, this system also comes with some challenges. Due to reduced communication with colleagues, women often feel isolated in the professional environment. Concerns about career growth and difficulty in maintaining managerial trust have also become common issues (Kaufman & Taniguchi, 2021; Church, 2015).

Women working from home also face several practical difficulties. These include a lack of proper workspace, unstable internet connectivity and an increasing burden of household chores (Vyas & Butakhieo, 2021). Feeling socially isolated and not having informal interactions with colleagues also affect productivity and career growth opportunities (Dahik et al., 2020; Larson et al., 2020). Additionally, sitting in one place for long hours, constant screen exposure causing eye strain and physical discomfort are problems that affect women in India more severely (Sharma & Vaish, 2020; Lim, 2020). The economic situation has also worsened due to the pandemic. According to a report, 41% of employees experienced stagnation in their careers, while 47% of self-employed women lost their jobs during this period (Mendoza, 2020; Suratkon & Azlan, 2021).

1.3. Impact of WFH on Work-Life Balance and Mental Well-being

WFH has had the biggest impact on work-life balance (WLB) and mental health. During the pandemic, the sudden implementation of the work-from-home system blurred the boundaries between work and personal life. As a result, employees had to manage both their professional and household responsibilities simultaneously, creating new challenges in their lives (Mariana Toniolo-Barrios & Pitt, 2020). Several studies have revealed that this transition negatively affected many people's motivation, productivity and mental health (Mariana Toniolo-Barrios & Pitt, 2020). To reduce these problems, the adoption of mindfulness techniques and efforts to improve the balance between work and family were suggested (Mariana Toniolo-Barrios & Pitt, 2020; Al-Habaibeh et al., 2021).

Working from home has also led to several mental health-related issues. In a study by Phadnis et al. (2021), 67% of employees reported increased workloads, which resulted in feelings of loneliness and isolation. Urrejola-Contreras (2023) highlighted that excessive workload and technology-related stress (technostress) contribute to mental fatigue and burnout, particularly among Generation X employees. Similarly, the study by Griep et al. (2022) found that if work hours are not properly controlled, mental health problems become more severe. In particular, long working hours have a greater impact on women.

However, if working hours are managed properly, these effects can be reduced. This highlights the importance of organisational support in maintaining employees' mental well-being (Griep et al., 2022).

The study by Kim et al. (2023) revealed that WFH generally has a negative impact on mental health. However, individuals with families and children tend to experience fewer difficulties. This indicates that family support and environment play an important role in maintaining emotional stability during remote work.

2. Problem statement

WFH has brought significant changes to the professional and personal lives of women. It not only affects their family relationships and emotional well-being but also impacts their work-life balance, stress levels and concentration ability. While WFH provides women with the freedom and flexibility to work, it has also introduced several new challenges. The biggest problem is that the boundaries between work and household responsibilities have become blurred. Additionally, the increased workload has led to higher stress levels and at times, maintaining concentration has become difficult (Phadnis et al., 2021; Urrejola-Contreras, 2023; Gorjifard & Crawford, 2021).

This study attempts to understand the experiences of women in the Delhi NCR who are working under WFH conditions. It examines both the positive and negative impacts of remote work on their professional and personal lives. The findings of this study will help in understanding what kind of workplace policies and support systems should be developed for women so that they can maintain a better balance while working remotely and remain mentally healthy.

3. Objective

- To analyse the impact of WFH on family dynamics and emotional well-being among women.
- To examine the effects of WFH on cognitive efficiency, stress levels and work-life balance among women.

4. Hypothesis

- **Hypothesis 1:** Women working from home experience both positive and negative effects on family happiness and work-life balance—some perceive increased family happiness due to more time spent at home, while others struggle with blurred boundaries leading to higher stress.
- **Hypothesis 2:** While work-from-home allows women to spend more time with family, it may also introduce distractions and cognitive inefficiencies, affecting productivity and overall well-being.

5. Significance of the Study

This study clearly explains how WFH affects women's emotional health, family relationships, work-life balance and concentration ability, especially its impact on women in Delhi NCR. The findings of this research will help employers, policymakers and organisations understand the benefits of remote work for women and the challenges they face. This will assist in developing better workplace policies, providing more support for mental health and creating flexible work options.

According to the research, the experience of WFH is different for every woman. Some women find it helpful in balancing their work and family life, while for others, it can increase stress and difficulties. Its impact depends on how the organisation functions, its policies and the personal circumstances of the woman (Xiao et al., 2020; Giovanis & Ozdamar, 2020). Additionally, this study highlights the specific challenges women face while working from home. The research will help in developing future work models that are more sustainable and inclusive for everyone.

6. Research Approach

Both quantitative and qualitative methods have been used in this research to gain a deeper understanding of the subject. This study has been carried out in the Delhi-NCR region, where 100 women have been included randomly. The process of data collection has been completed using a structured questionnaire and interview method to better understand women's experiences.

Correlation analysis has been used in the research to determine the impact of WFH on family happiness, stress levels and concentration ability. In addition, frequency distribution has been applied to observe how similar or different the opinions and experiences of various women have been. The results of the research have been presented through charts and (Chart 1).

Chart: 1 Overview of Research Approach

(Source: Created by Author)

7. Data Analysis and Discussion

Women working from home felt an increase in family happiness when they spent more time with their families. Study found that there was a moderate positive relationship between time spent with family and family happiness ($r = 0.385$), which was statistically significant at the 0.01 level ($p = 0.000$). This means that as women spent more time with their families, their sense of family happiness also increased. The results of this research confirmed that working from home gave women the opportunity to spend more time with their families, leading to an increase in family happiness (Table 1).

Table:1 Correlation Between Family Happiness and Time Spent with Family

Correlations		Happiness	Time
Happiness	Pearson Correlation	1	.385**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	100	100
Time	Pearson Correlation	.385**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	100	100

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

(Source: Created by Author)

It was expected that an increased workload or unclear boundaries between work and personal life would lead to higher stress levels. However, when the relationship between time and stress was analysed, the Pearson correlation coefficient was found to be 0.114, indicating a very weak positive relationship. This means that as time increased, stress levels rose slightly, but there was no strong connection between the two. The p-value (Sig. 2-tailed) was 0.258, which was greater than 0.05. This clearly means that in this study, the relationship between time and stress was not found to be statistically significant at the 5% level (Table 1).

Table: 2 Correlation Between Time and Stress

Correlations		Time	Stress
Time	Pearson Correlation	1	.114
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.258
	N	100	100
Stress	Pearson Correlation	.114	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.258	
	N	100	100

(Source: Created by Author)

Due to working from home, women had gotten the opportunity to spend more time with their families. According to the analysis conducted, 59 percent of women had reported that they had spent significantly more time with their families compared to before. Meanwhile, 21 percent of women had said that there had been only a slight increase in the time spent with their families, while only 2 percent of women had felt that they had spent less time than before. This clearly showed that most women had benefited from spending more time with their families while working from home. Since 59 percent of women had described this as a positive experience, this hypothesis was proven to be correct (Chart 2).

Chart:2 Frequency Distribution of Time Spent with Family While Working from Home

Time Spent with Family While Working from Home

(Source: Created by Author)

Due to working from home, women had faced various distractions, which had affected their cognitive efficiency. The study had found that 68 percent of women had reported that their efficiency had decreased due to frequent distractions during work. Meanwhile, 32 percent of women had said that they had not experienced any such issue and their efficiency had remained the same as before. This had clearly shown that for most women, working from home had been a challenging experience, as their ability to work had been affected due to distractions. Since a large number of women had admitted to a decline in their efficiency, this study had concluded that the hypothesis had been proven correct (Chart 3).

Chart:3 Impact of WFH on Cognitive Efficiency Due to Distractions

Impact of WFH Distractions on Cognitive Efficiency

(Source: Created by Author)

Working from home had a mixed impact on women's work-life balance. Some women benefited from it and were able to maintain a better balance between their work and family responsibilities. However, many women faced difficulties due to unclear boundaries between work and home. According to the study conducted, 39 percent of women reported that their work and personal life boundaries had completely blurred, causing them stress. 32 percent of women said that they faced this issue to some extent. Additionally, 23 percent of women experienced only minor difficulties, while 6 percent of women stated that they did not face any such problem. This clearly shows that most women had difficulty maintaining a work-life balance while working from home. Since the majority of women reported experiencing this problem, the hypothesis was proven to be correct (Chart 4).

Chart:4 Work-Life Balance Challenges Faced by Women Working from Home

(Source: Created by Author)

Discussion: This study helps in better understanding the impact of WFH, especially in terms of women's family happiness, stress levels, concentration and work-life balance. According to the study, working from home allowed women to spend more time with their families, bringing positive changes to their family life. This aligns with research findings that suggest remote work can help strengthen family relationships. However, while spending more time with family increased happiness, maintaining a balance between professional and household responsibilities remained challenging. The study also found that there was a very weak relationship between working hours and stress levels. This means that simply working longer hours does not increase stress. Other factors, such as workload, household responsibilities and mental resilience, also play an important role in determining stress levels. This finding suggests that not just working hours but also personal circumstances and mental attitude are crucial in determining stress levels while working from home. Additionally, the study clearly showed that most women acknowledged that WFH gave them the opportunity to spend more time with their families. This proves that working from home can have a positive impact on family relationships, although the extent of this impact may vary based on individual experiences. Some women enjoyed spending more time with their families, while others found it difficult to balance personal and professional life. At the same time, WFH also had a negative impact on women's concentration and work efficiency. The study found that many women faced

difficulties due to distractions at home. The lack of a quiet and structured office-like environment affected their productivity. Many women also experienced a decline in work efficiency due to the need to multitask. This finding supports research that suggests a well-organized workspace and clear boundaries help improve productivity. Work-life balance also remained a major challenge for women. Most women admitted that WFH blurred the boundaries between their work and personal life. This made it difficult for them to maintain a proper balance. This means that although WFH provides flexibility, clear rules and a disciplined approach are needed to avoid mental stress and maintain work-life balance. Overall, this study shows that WFH has several advantages, such as the opportunity to spend more time with family and flexible work hours. However, it also presents challenges related to productivity, stress management and work-life balance. These findings can be useful for policymakers and organisations in designing policies that make WFH more convenient and effective for women.

8. Conclusion

The findings of the study suggest that working from home has had both positive and negative impacts on women's lives. On one hand, they spent more time with their families, strengthening family relationships and increasing happiness. Some women also experienced a better work-life balance due to remote work. However, many struggled to maintain a balance between work and personal responsibilities, as the boundaries between the two were blurred. Frequent disturbances in the home environment affected their concentration and work efficiency. An interesting finding was that there was no clear relationship between working hours and stress, indicating that external factors such as workload, household responsibilities and mental resilience played a more significant role.

Recommendations for Employers and Women Working from Home:

Employers can support women working from home by implementing flexible work hours, allowing them to manage their workload more effectively. Additionally, they can provide mental health support and productivity training to enhance their well-being and efficiency. To maintain a clear distinction between work and home life, fixed working hours and structured remote work policies can be introduced, helping women balance their personal and professional responsibilities. On the other hand, women working from home can improve their work experience by creating a dedicated workspace, reducing distractions and focusing better on their tasks. They can set certain rules with family members to minimise interruptions during work and ensure a smooth workflow. Additionally, taking regular short breaks can help improve

their mental well-being and work efficiency, enabling them to work more effectively and maintain a balanced approach to their responsibilities.

9. Limitation and Future scope

This study is limited to 100 female respondents from Delhi-NCR, so it may not fully represent the experiences of women from different regions or larger groups. Since this is a short-term study, it cannot assess the long-term impact of work from home (WFH) on women's mental health, work-life balance and concentration. Additionally, the personal experiences of the women included in this study may vary, leading to differences in their responses.

Future research can include more women and expand to different geographic regions, making the findings more comprehensive and reliable. A long-term study on this topic can help understand the effects of WFH on women's mental health, productivity and work-life balance over time. Additionally, including women from different professional sectors and analysing the support systems provided by organisations will be important. Further research can also explore how technological tools, mental health measures and flexible work policies can help improve the WFH experience.

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